

Methodology of teaching physical culture

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Annotation: Physical culture is historically realized, first of all, in the process of preparing the younger generation and adults for creative work, under the influence of the practical requirements of society. At the same time, in the formation of a system of teaching and educating physical culture in society, as a key factor in the formation of various motor skills and abilities and the expansion of human activity opportunities, physical abilities, as well as intellectual, moral and aesthetic education helps to increase.

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What should be taken as a basic concept of physical culture? Before stating its principle, let's look at some of the cultural issues that can help explain its essence. The general concept of "culture" is often compared to the concept of mastering and changing nature and being. The concept of nature includes all living and non-living things in the world that do not depend on man and are not the result of his activities, that exist according to the laws of nature, and are not changed by man. The phenomenon of culture is the way and results of human activity that change nature and society, that is, the activity that meets the needs of man, aimed at changing nature. In the process of cultural development, there are types of activities (forms, methods) that are aimed at self-improvement and change of personal nature.

An integral part of such a culture is physical culture. Physical culture influences a person's life qualities and abilities. They are taken from nature as a great blessing and passed down from generation to generation. Physical culture, as the genetic basis of development, develops over the course of a generation's life, under the influence of living conditions, activities, and upbringing. Of course, neither man nor society as a whole can overturn or change the laws of their objective development, because they exist independently of man. For example, the laws of gradual quantitative and qualitative changes in the body, the law of functional and structural changes in the body, the relationship of the organism to living conditions, and so on. However, along with these laws, it is possible to influence the process of natural development (including the

physical development of the organism) by raising the general culture of society. On the one hand, physical culture helps to nurture focused physical qualities and abilities by purposefully influencing a person's physical development process. Human physical development is influenced by social living conditions, upbringing, including physical education, genetics and the process of acceleration. Physical culture is historically realized, first of all, in the process of preparing the younger generation and adults for creative work, under the influence of the practical requirements of society. At the same time, in the formation of a system of teaching and educating physical culture in society, as a key factor in the formation of various motor skills and abilities and the expansion of human activity opportunities, physical abilities, as well as intellectual, moral and aesthetic education helps to increase. In the context of technological development, changes in the nature of work and living conditions, as a great wealth in changing a person's physical culture, prevent disease, improve the functioning of the body's functions, increase and maintain performance, in general, protect human health and the growth and importance of physical culture in strengthening is great.

At each stage in the development of physical culture, the content as a wealth that satisfies the vital needs of man has evolved. Here we are talking about the most common methods of physical culture today: gymnastics, sports, sports games, practical and other sections of physical culture as a set of exercises.

According to the purpose, the types of movement activities developed, the riches in the field of physical culture, directly specific practical knowledge, principles, rules and methods of exercise, ethical norms, are reflected in the relationships between people in the process of physical culture activities. Success in sports depends on the material, technical and other conditions specially designed to increase the effectiveness of physical culture in society. Medical supplies, sports information - reflective art products, sports facilities, special tools and equipment - are the riches of physical culture.

Of course, not all of this applies to physical culture alone, as many of these are not only related to physical culture, but also to the mixed sciences in the field of culture. The development of physical culture depends on the performance of certain tasks, its use in a defined way in the conditions of life in society, its clear value and role. Depending on the circumstances, physical culture can affect a person in different ways (unilaterally or in all directions).

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In society, physical culture, in the harmonious development of the individual, not only as a factor of physical maturity, but also as a means of moral, aesthetic, intellectual education, along with other aspects of culture, contributes to the full development of all members of society. Socially oriented use of physical culture not only contributes to economic growth and protection of the Motherland, but also as a means of satisfying the spiritual needs of the people, the harmonious development of the individual, the organization of a healthy lifestyle important.